

BIOCHAR AS AN ALTERNATIVE FILLER FOR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) is a tropical fruit of significant economic importance in Brazil, largely consumed in its immature stage, which contains a high volume of coconut water. However, its widespread consumption results in considerable waste generation. The accumulation of this lignocellulosic biomass contributes to the reduction of landfill lifespan, raising environmental concerns. As an abundant and renewable resource, this biomass represents a promising alternative to fossil-derived materials and a potential feedstock for producing biochar via thermochemical processes such as pyrolysis. Biochar exhibits properties like high hydrophobicity, improved compatibility with polymer matrices, and enhanced thermal stability compared to conventional filler materials. In this context, coconut fiber was investigated for composite applications. Its physicochemical characterization revealed an amount of lignin (insoluble Klason lignin) of approximately 32.0% (w/w). Pyrolysis of the fiber yielded a significant amount of biochar, with CHNSO elemental analysis confirming a high carbon content. Subsequent FTIR spectroscopy verified the successful conversion of biomass into biochar, while TGA/DTG analysis demonstrated its thermal stability. Finally, mechanical testing indicated that coconut-derived biochar holds promise as a sustainable filler for polymer composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The coconut fruit (*Cocos nucifera*) originates from the coconut palm and is cultivated in over 90 countries, with its primary use in the food industry [1]. According to the latest data from Faostat (2021), the global harvested area of coconuts covers approximately 11.8 million hectares, yielding 62.9 million tons. Three countries - Indonesia, Philippines, and India – account for 73.0% of the cultivated area and 74.1% of the total production. Brazil ranks as

the world's fourth-largest coconut producer, with an estimated output of 2.8 million tons from 257,000 hectares, of which around 15% is destined for the green coconut market [2].

The rising consumption of coconut water (100 to 350 million liters per year), fueled by increasing health-conscious behavior among Brazilians, led to a challenge regarding the disposal of coconut shells, which constitute 80 - 85% of the fruit's total weight. Commonly discarded in open dumps, landfills and unauthorized areas, these residues not only cause visual pollution and unpleasant odors but also promote disease transmission. Under anaerobic conditions, their decomposition generates methane, a potent greenhouse gas. Although organic in nature, coconut waste is highly resistant to degradation and can take more than 8 years to fully decompose [3].

Extracted from the coconut mesocarp, these fibers are primarily composed of cellulose and hemicellulose and contain a high lignin content (20–48%) [4]. To add value and reduce the environmental impact of this waste, various alternatives have been explored for the utilization of coconut fiber. As a lignocellulosic material, it represents a promising renewable and eco-friendly alternative to fossil resources, especially as a raw material for energy production. Pyrolysis is among the most widely adopted processes for converting biomass into biochar, gas, and bio-oil [5,6]. This process involves the thermal decomposition of the three main components—cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin—in the absence of oxygen [7,8]. Coconut fiber and its pyrolysis product, biochar, are both promising for various applications. The high lignin content in coconut fibers gives them notable hardness and durability compared to other natural fibers [9], and their incorporation into composite materials has been widely studied [10,11]. The thermal and acoustic properties of coconut fiber-based materials can vary depending on origin and processing, but they have demonstrated thermal conductivity and sound absorption values comparable to those of conventional synthetic insulation materials such as polyurethane boards, glass wool, and rock wool [11].

Biochar, because of its carbon-rich and porous structure, stands out as a multifunctional material [12]. Beyond its role in carbon sequestration—preventing CO₂ release into the atmosphere [13]—biochar also improves soil fertility, water retention, and microbial activity when applied as a soil amendment [14,15]. More recently, its potential as a filler in polymer composites has gained attention. Biochar can enhance the mechanical strength, thermal stability, and even flame-retardant properties of composites [16], making it an attractive material for the development of high-performance, sustainable products.

This study aims to contribute to the development of environmentally friendly materials with enhanced performance. The objective was to produce biochar from coconut fiber, characterize the physical-chemical, structural, and thermal properties of both raw and pyrolyzed materials, and prepare composite materials using coconut fiber and biochar as fillers. Finally, the mechanical properties of the resulting composites were evaluated.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The materials used in this study included coconut fiber supplied by Coco Verde Reciclado, epoxy resin (Epoxy Fiber MC 130) and curing agent (Epoxy Fiber 129), both provided by Epoxyfiber LTDA, and absolute ethanol obtained from Isofar LTDA. The coconut fiber was initially ground using a knife mill (model SL-31, Solab), and the resulting fractions were classified using a set of sieves (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Original coconut fiber (a) and coconut fiber ground (b)

BIOCHAR PRODUCTION

The pyrolysis reaction was performed using coconut fiber to study the reaction conditions. The process was conducted in a bench-scale stainless steel reactor under a continuous nitrogen flow to ensure an inert atmosphere. A total of 5 g of coconut fiber (20 mesh), previously dried to constant weight, was used. The nitrogen (N₂) flow rate was set at 80 mL/min, the reaction temperature was 500 °C, and the total residence time was 30 minutes. Gaseous products were collected during the reaction in Tedlar bags. The mass yields of the condensable fraction and solid residue were determined by direct weighing, while the yield of the gaseous fraction was calculated by difference. The resulting material was referred to as laboratory coconut fiber biochar (LCFB).

A second pyrolysis process was carried out in a semi-pilot stainless steel reactor (6 L capacity) under similar conditions. A total of 1000 g of coconut fiber (60–100 mesh), also dried to constant weight, was used. The nitrogen flow rate was 200 mL/min, the temperature was maintained at 500 °C, and the reaction time was extended to 120 minutes. The condensable fraction and solid residue were quantified by direct weighing of the collection vessels, while the gaseous fraction was obtained by mass balance. The solid product was identified as coconut fiber biochar (CFB) from the pilot unit.

Physical and chemical characterization

Coconut fiber with a particle size of 0.85 mm (20 mesh) was used for physicochemical analysis. Samples were dried at 60 °C until constant weight for the determination of extractives, lignin content, and CHNSO elemental composition.

The analyzed samples included raw coconut fiber and the corresponding biochar. Moisture content, ash content, and pH of both coconut fiber and CFB were determined using standard procedures established by EMBRAPA [17]. The percentages of extractives and lignin in the fiber were also determined. Elemental analysis (CHNSO) was performed using a UNICUBE elemental analyzer (Elementar, Germany).

Structural and thermal analysis

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) was performed using a PerkinElmer Frontier FT-IR spectrometer. Samples were pelletized with potassium bromide (KBr) at a concentration of 1% (w/w). Spectra were obtained by averaging 32 scans at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted using a PerkinElmer Pyris One TGA instrument under an inert nitrogen atmosphere, with a flow rate of 25 mL/min and a heating rate of 10 °C/min, from room temperature up to 800 °C.

TENSILE STRENGTH OF COCONUT FIBRE AND COCONUT FIBRE BIOCHAR COMPOSITES

Composite of coir fiber and coconut fiber biochar

To prepare the test specimens, the following materials were used: epoxy resin (Epoxy Fiber MC 130), amine hardener (Epoxy Fiber 129), absolute ethanol, and coconut fiber with a particle size of 0.85 mm (20 mesh). For the composite formulations, coconut fiber biochar (CFB) was used in fine powder form. Both the fiber and biochar materials were dried in an oven at 105 °C prior to use.

The test specimens were prepared using a 100 mm × 100 mm Teflon mold spacer. Fillers (either FC or CFB) were randomly dispersed within the epoxy matrix. The resin-to-filler ratio was set at 60:40 (by weight). For every 10 parts of resin, 1 part of hardener and 1 part of ethanol were added to aid mixing and dispersion, as detailed in Table 1. The curing process involved compression molding: 10 minutes in a cold press, followed by 10 minutes in a hot press, and an additional 10 minutes in a cold press.

Materials	Mass (g)	Volume (ml)
Epoxy Resin (Fiber MC 130)	27.0	---
Amine Hardener (Epoxy Fiber 129)	2.7	---
Ethanol	2.7	3.42
FC or CFB	18.0	---

Table 1: Materials and quantities used in the composite

Mechanical properties and standards used

Mechanical testing was conducted using an Instron Electropuls E3000 universal electromechanical testing machine, equipped with a 5 kN Dynacell load cell, an Instron 2630-106 extensometer, and 3 kN-capacity Instron mechanical grips. Thickness measurements were taken using a Digimes digital external micrometer (model 113.054 B). The crosshead speed was set at 2.0 mm/min under ambient conditions of 27 ± 2 °C and $46 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity.

The mechanical properties of the epoxy composites containing FC or CFB were evaluated according to ASTM D3039/D3039M standards.

3 RESULTS

Physical and chemical characterization

The physicochemical characteristics of the coconut fiber used in this study are presented in Table 2 and were obtained following rigorous standardized methods. The values obtained slightly differ from those reported in the literature, as such parameters are strongly influenced by the geographic origin and processing conditions of the biomass. Ash content showed the greatest variation, which is likely related to the mineral salts present in the cultivation area. Other parameters exhibited strong agreement with values reported in the literature.

Analisis	Coconuts Fiber	Reference
Moisture (%)	8.79 ± 0,16	6.75 [18]
Ash (%)	1.02 ± 0,01	3.38 [18]
pH	6.06 ± 0,07	6.4[4]
Insoluble lignin ^a (%)	32.07 ± 0,20	20–48[4,19]
Extractives (%)	2.66 ± 0.21	-
C (%)	47.42 ± 0,07	47.6 [20]
H (%)	5.92 ± 0,01	5.7 [20]
N (%)	0.28 ± 0.01	0.2 [20]
S (%)	0.12 0.01	-

a. Ash and protein free; (-): not observed.

Table 2: Physical and chemical characterization of coconut fiber

Biochar production

Pyrolysis reactions were conducted both at the laboratory scale to achieve the best reaction conditions and at the pilot scale to produce sufficient quantities for composite fabrication. Following pyrolysis, three product fractions were obtained: condensable liquids, volatile gases, and solid residue (biochar). Table 3 presents the yields of biochar produced from coconut fiber under identical temperature conditions at the laboratory scale (LCFB) and pilot scale (CFB). It was observed that the yield of solid residue from the laboratory-scale pyrolysis was slightly higher than that obtained from the pilot plant (CFB). This difference is attributed to the higher nitrogen flow rate used in the pilot plant, which favored the formation of volatile products.

Sample	Mass (g)	Condensable (%)	Volatile (%)	Solid residue (%)
LCFB	5	48,2	20,4	31,4
CFB	1000	40,1	36,5	23,4

Table 3: Results of pyrolysis reactions of coconut fiber

Structural and thermal analysis

Figure 6 shows the ATR-FTIR spectra of coconut fiber (CF) samples and biochar obtained from coconut fiber (CFB). In the coconut fiber spectrum, the broad band observed between 3600 and 3200 cm⁻¹ corresponds to O–H stretching vibrations associated with the hydroxyl groups present in the biomass macromolecules, namely cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The presence of lignin is confirmed by characteristic signals attributed to aromatic rings (5). The band near 2900 cm⁻¹ corresponds to aliphatic C–H stretching linked to the aromatic ring [21]. The intense band at 1747 cm⁻¹ (3) indicates the presence of ketone, carbonyl, and ester functional groups [4]. This is followed by peaks at 1607 cm⁻¹ and 1506 cm⁻¹ (4 and 5), which are assigned to the C=O conjugated and C=C stretching in the aromatic rings of lignin [22]. The peak at 1467 cm⁻¹ (6) is attributed to C–H bending vibrations. The peak at 1321 cm⁻¹ (7) corresponds to C–H deformation of methyl groups and O–H of phenolic structures [4].

The peak at 1238 cm^{-1} (8) is related to C–C, C–O, and C=O stretching in the guaiacyl units of lignin [22]. Peaks observed between 1160 and 990 cm^{-1} (9) are attributed to β -glycosidic bonds present in cellulose.

In the CFB spectra, a reduction in several characteristic peaks of coconut fiber is observed, notably the absorption band between 1400 and 907 cm^{-1} (10). Furthermore, the peak attributed to the β -glycosidic bond (peak 9) is no longer detected, indicating that pyrolysis effectively decomposed cellulose components.

Figure 2: FTIR results for coconut fiber (CF) and coconut fiber biochar (CFB).

The thermal stability of coconut fiber and coconut fiber biochar was evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (Figure 3). The decomposition of coconut fiber components occurs within characteristic temperature ranges: hemicellulose, because of its amorphous structure, decomposes between 200 – $260\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; cellulose between 240 – $360\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; and lignin between 280 – $360\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [23].

In the thermogram of coconut fiber, two major events were observed. The first, occurring below $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, corresponds to moisture loss. The second event comprises two degradation stages. The first stage, from $203\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $315\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, is associated with the decomposition of hemicellulose and part of the cellulose. The second stage, from $315\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $492\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, corresponds to the degradation of lignin and the remaining cellulose. The maximum rate of mass loss was observed at $301\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (T_{onset}). Therefore, significant lignin degradation and the formation of biochar only occur above $492\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is the temperature range of interest for this study.

For the coconut fiber biochar, the thermogram indicated enhanced thermal stability, consistent with the thermal behavior observed for lignin-derived pyrolysis products [24]. The DTG curve for the biochar showed two main events. The first was a minor peak associated with residual moisture loss. The second, a single-stage degradation event, occurred between $337\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $640\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a maximum degradation rate (T_{onset}) at $446\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a peak degradation temperature at $547\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. These findings are in agreement with values reported in the literature and are attributed to the carbonization of biomass and the formation of stable carbon structures [25].

Tensile strength of coconut fibre and coconut fibre biochar composites

The tensile strength and tensile modulus of epoxy resin-based composites were evaluated to investigate the effect of incorporating coconut fiber and biochar. The addition of biochar significantly influenced the mechanical performance of the composites. Acting as a reinforcing filler, biochar enhanced the load-bearing capacity of the material, likely because of its porous structure and high surface area, which improve interfacial adhesion within the polymer matrix [26].

Figure 3: TGA and DTG results for coconut fiber (CF) and coconut fiber biochar (CFB)

In this study, the final composite plates produced with coconut fiber or coconut fiber biochar as fillers and epoxy resin as the matrix exhibited homogeneous structure, smooth surfaces, and moderate gloss (Figure 4). No bubbles or surface roughness were observed. The composite reinforced with coconut fiber showed a tensile modulus of 3.63 GPa, whereas the composite containing biochar (CFB) exhibited a higher modulus of 4.48 GPa. This indicates that incorporating biochar significantly enhances the stiffness of the composite, likely due to improved filler–matrix interfacial interactions. Table 4 presents the tensile test data for both composites, and the corresponding results are graphically represented in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Coconut Fiber (a) and Coconut Fiber Biochar Composites (b)

Sample	Strain (MPa)	Stress (%)	Tensile modulus (GPa)
FC	26.59 ± 0.99	0.79 ± 0.05	3.63 ± 0.18
CFB	20.42 ± 2.21	0.45 ± 0.02	4.48 ± 0.53

Table 4: Mechanical properties of epoxy composites with Coconut Fiber (CF) and Coconut Fiber Biochar (CFB)

Figure 5: Mechanical properties of epoxy composites with Coconut Fiber (CF) and Coconut Fiber Biochar (CFB)

4 CONCLUSIONS

Coconut fiber is a natural lignocellulosic material with a high lignin content compared to other plant-based fibers, which makes it a promising candidate for applications across various industrial sectors. This study evaluated the use of biochar derived from coconut fiber as a reinforcing filler in epoxy resin composites.

FTIR and TGA analyses confirmed that the pyrolysis conditions were favorable for biochar production, evidencing structural and thermal transformations. Mechanical testing demonstrated the viability and effectiveness of incorporating biochar, with a modest but significant increase in tensile modulus—from 3.6 GPa for the coconut fiber composite to 4.3 GPa for the biochar-reinforced composite.

These findings suggest that both coconut fiber and its biochar can serve as sustainable, environmentally friendly alternatives to conventional fillers in composite materials.

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